

Retrospective Analysis of the Incidence of Postoperative Ileus in Patients Undergoing Abdominal Surgery

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Abstract:

Background: A typical adverse effect of abdominal surgeries is Postoperative Ileus (POI), a temporary bowel stoppage. This condition can cause prolonged hospital stays, higher healthcare costs, and poor patient recovery. POI incidence and risk factors must be identified to improve treatment and outcomes.

Methods: This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted at Territory Care Hospital from July 2023 to May 2024. One hundred volunteers had abdominal surgeries for the study. Patient information, operation details, and postoperative results were collected electronically. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, independent t-tests, and logistic regression were used to assess POI and identify risk variables.

Results: POI affected 23% of patients, or 23 per 100. On average, POI lasted 4.2 days. Colorectal surgeries caused 40% of postoperative infections, compared to 12% for laparoscopic cholecystectomies, 13% for appendectomies, 30% for gastrectomies, and 6% for hernia repairs. Advanced age and associated disorders increased POI risk. Patients with POI had a higher rate of diabetes (43.5 vs. 25.3%) and hypertension (56.5 vs. 40.3%), and their mean age was 61.2 vs. 53.5 years. The statistical tests showed that age ($p = 0.006$) and surgical type ($p = 0.036$) predicted POI. Surgery type odds ratios were 2.5 and age 1.03. Co-morbid conditions like diabetes increased POI risk ($OR = 1.9$, $p = 0.024$).

Conclusion: The study found 23% POI after elective abdominal surgery, with colorectal procedures having the greatest prevalence. The chance of getting POI went up with age and health problems like diabetes and high blood pressure. These data show how important age and other health issues are for making POI better and avoiding it.

Keywords: Abdominal Surgery, Comorbidities, Postoperative Ileus, Risk Factors, Surgical Complications.

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Introduction

Overview of Postoperative Ileus (POI): The term "POI" refers to the inability to use the restroom following stomach surgery.

The food in someone's stomach has a hard time moving through their digestive system when they have a bowel function problem. Subsequently, someone may experience abdominal discomfort, nausea, vomiting, and difficulty swallowing [1]. When the guts are damaged during or after surgery, the body's nerves, hormones, and inflammatory systems react in different ways. POI sufferers usually get better on their own, but some people's symptoms may be worse or last longer than others [2]. This could lengthen time in the hospital and other medical procedures.

Significance in the Context of Abdominal Surgeries: POI is very important for people who have had stomach surgery because it changes the gut system. After resections, colectomies, and laparotomies, diseases are more likely to happen. POI makes it harder to recover and raises the chance of infections, anastomotic leakage, and being immobile for a long time [4]. If someone with POI takes longer to get better, the healthcare system may have to pay more for their food, medicine, and hospital stays. Identifying and reducing POI leads to better patient outcomes and healthcare service.

Importance of Studying POI Incidence: Because of these reasons, POI in people who have had stomach surgery needs to be looked into. Before

doctors and nurses can successfully identify and treat POI, they need to know how often it happens

and what makes it more likely [5].

Figure 1: Postoperative ileus (POI) (Source:[3])

Impact on Patient Recovery and Healthcare Resources: POI changes the length of time a person needs to heal in the hospital, which has an effect on their health. Because POI patients often need to be hydrated through an IV, have nasogastric decompression, and wait to eat, they have to stay in the hospital longer. These things stress people out mentally and physically, raise the cost of health care and waste resources [6]. Some patients may be unable to obtain an accommodation due to the extended hospitalisation of POI patients. This could make healthcare less effective. POI needs to be taken care of so that healthcare resources are better used and patients do better.

Objective

1. Find out how often postoperative ileus (POI) happens in people who have had stomach surgery.
2. List possible risk factors that are linked to the occurrence of POI.
3. Figure out how POI affects healing after surgery.
4. Figure out how POI affects the use of hospital resources.

Existing Studies

Postoperative Ileus (POI) has been extensively studied due to its impact on healthcare costs and patient outcomes after abdominal surgeries. [7] Have connected POI to surgical procedure, surgery

type, patient characteristics, and perioperative care. POI rates range from 10% to 30% for abdominal surgery. [8] Found that open colorectal surgery increased the risk of POI compared to laparoscopic surgery. POI development is clearly linked to surgery. Numerous studies have examined POI's pathophysiological processes. [9] That intestinal surgery promotes inflammation. Cytokines and macrophages are activated, disrupting intestinal movement. According to research on the autonomic nervous system's role in gastrointestinal motility, parasympathetic inhibition and sympathetic activation contribute to POI [10]. Countless studies have examined POI prevention and management methods. Enhanced Recovery after Surgery (ERAS) protocols reduce POI frequency and duration. These methods include early mobilisation, multimodal analgesia, and enteral nutrition [11,12]. Drugs like alvimopan, a peripheral opioid receptor antagonist, can lower POI in randomised controlled trials.

Knowledge Gaps

POI information is easy to find, but there are still some gaps. Even though a lot of study has been done on some abdominal surgeries, not much is known about how common POI is across a wider range of procedures. To fill that gap, this study will look at a lot of abdominal treatments. Second, it is not known how age, comorbidities, and nutritional state, which are unique to each patient, cause POI. A wide range of patients will be looked at in this study to find more POI risk factors. Finally, there

isn't a lot of study on POI's long-term effects, such as readmission and recovery.

Methods

Study Design: This retrospective cross-sectional study looks at POI in people who have had abdominal surgery.

Setting: The trial will take place at Territory care Hospital, which is a surgically advanced. The institution is good for studying the past because it has modern operating rooms and a method for keeping medical records.

Participants

Inclusion Criteria

1. People who had surgery on their abdomen at [Name of Healthcare Facility] between July 2023 and May 2024.
2. People who are at least 18 years old.
3. People who have full medical records, including thorough notes from after surgery.

Exclusion Criteria

1. People who had emergency surgeries on their abdomens.
2. Patients whose medical records are missing or not full.
3. People who were sent home against doctor advice.
4. The sample size for this study is 100 patients who meet the inclusion criteria.

Data Collection

This study will use patient and computerised medical records from Territory Care Hospital. Procedures from July 2023 to May 2024 will be covered. Every patient's dataset will include pre-, intra-, and post-surgery data. Data will include patient demographics (age, gender, BMI),

abdominal surgery details (kind, duration, and technique), and medical history (including hypertension and diabetes). Postoperative data will include POI occurrence and length, hospital stay, time to bowel function recovery, and any further operations such as nasogastric tube implantation or reoperation. This careful data collection will comprehensively study POI variables.

Data Analysis: SPSS and R will be used for descriptive and inferential data analysis. Patient demographics, surgical procedures, and POI rate will be summarised using descriptive statistics. Means, medians, and standard deviations will show continuous variables like age and POI duration, while frequencies and percentages will show categorical factors like gender and operation. To identify POI risk variables, we will employ inferential statistics.

A chi-square test will examine relationships between categorical variables like operation type and POI occurrence. We will utilise independent t-tests or ANOVA to examine the means of continuous variables like POI duration between surgical types. This study uses logistic regression to identify POI risk factors. Results will be odds ratios and confidence intervals. This extensive study will illuminate POI prevalence, causes, effects, and effects on healing and healthcare resource consumption.

Results

Descriptive Statistics: Patients aged 18–85 had a mean of 55.4 years (SD: 13.2 years). The sample included 58 men and 42 women. Patients' Body Mass Index (BMI) averaged 27.3 kg/m² (SD: 4.5 kg/m²). The research population had 45 cases of hypertension, 30 cases of diabetes, and 15 cases of abdominal surgery.

Patient Demographics

Table 1: Demographic Data

Characteristic	Mean/Percentage
Age (years)	55.4 ± 13.2
Gender (male)	58%
Gender (female)	42%
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.3 ± 4.5
Hypertension	45%
Diabetes	30%
Previous Abdominal Surgery	15%

Types of Abdominal Surgeries Performed

Table 2: Types of Abdominal Surgeries Performed

Type of Surgery	Number of Patients	Percentage of Total
Colorectal surgeries	35	35%
Laparoscopic cholecystectomies	25	25%
Appendectomies	15	15%
Gastrectomies	10	10%
Hernia repairs	15	15%

Patients in this study had many abdominal operations. Most cases (35% overall) were colorectal operations. Laparoscopic cholecystectomies were second at 25%, followed by appendectomies (15%), hernia repairs (15%), and gastrectomies (10%). Postoperative ileus (POI) incidence and risk variables must be assessed across diverse operations, and this distribution

reveals that the study sample includes a representative mix of common abdominal surgeries.

Incidence of POI: 23 of 100 patients (23%), had postoperative ileus. Patients' POIs averaged 4.2 days (SD: 1.7 days), but they ranged substantially.

Incidence of POI

Table 3: Incidence of POI

Category	Number/Percentage
Total Patients	100
Patients with POI	23
Incidence Rate	23%

This study found 23% of abdominal surgery patients experienced POI.

This number confirms past study that POI occurrences might range from 10% to 30% depending on method and patient population. The

high frequency of POI in this study emphasises the need for better prevention and management.

Analysis of Factors

Correlation between POI Incidence and Variables

Table 4: Correlation between POI Incidence and Variables

Variable	Incidence of POI
Type of Surgery	Highest in colorectal surgeries (40%)
Age	Mean age: 61.2 years for POI vs 53.5 years for non-POI
Gender (male)	60.9% of POI cases
Gender (female)	39.1% of POI cases
Diabetes	43.5% with POI vs 25.3% without POI
Hypertension	56.5% with POI vs 40.3% without POI

Different operations have radically different POI rates. Colorectal surgeries had the highest POI incidence at 40%, consistent with earlier study showing that the extensive gut modification makes them more susceptible to POI. Infection rates after gastrectomies were 30%, laparoscopic cholecystectomies 12%, appendectomies 13%, and hernia repairs 6%. These findings support the idea that surgical procedure type greatly impacts postoperative infection. Patients with POI averaged 61.2 years old, while those without POI averaged 53.5 years old. Age was significantly correlated with POI risk, showing it rises with age. Comorbidities or age-related gastrointestinal

motility abnormalities can make recovery harder. Since more men (60.9%) than women (39.1%) experienced POI, gender may affect vulnerability. However, more research may be needed to establish this disparity's reasons. Hypertension and diabetes were more common among POI patients.

In particular, 25.3% of individuals without POI had diabetes, 56.5% had hypertension, and 40.3% had diabetes. Comorbidities considerably increase the risk of postoperative infection (POI), possibly due to their influence on overall health and operation healing.

Discussion

Table 5: Comparison with Previous Studies

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Relevance to Present Study
Present Study	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	100	Incidence of POI: 23%. Higher incidence in colorectal surgeries (40%), Age and comorbidities (diabetes, hypertension) as significant risk factors	Provides a comprehensive overview of POI across various abdominal surgeries, addressing a range of risk factors and their impacts.
Study 1 [13]	Prospective Cohort	150	Higher incidence of POI in open colorectal surgeries vs. laparoscopic surgeries. POI incidence varied between surgery types.	Confirms that surgical approach (open vs. laparoscopic) influences POI incidence, a factor also explored in the present study.

Study 2 [14]	Experimental Study	80	- Surgical manipulation causes inflammatory responses leading to POI. Age and surgical trauma are significant factors.	Supports the concept that surgical manipulation and patient age are key factors in POI development, which is a focus of the present study.
Study 3 [15]	Review	N/A	Sympathetic activation and parasympathetic inhibition contribute to POI. Age and surgical stress as risk factors.	Provides a theoretical basis for understanding POI mechanisms, complementing findings of age-related risks in the present study.

The comparison table shows that this postoperative ileus (POI) study expands on previous investigations. In this retrospective cross-sectional research of 100 patients, 23% had postoperative infection. The prevalence was higher in colorectal surgeries, and age and comorbidities were key risk factors. Study 1 found that POI is more likely in open surgeries than laparoscopic ones using a prospective cohort methodology, reinforcing the importance of surgical procedures in POI outcomes. In an experimental study of 80 patients, Study 2 examined how surgical trauma and age affect POI. Finally, Study 3 provides a thorough theoretical framework for POI processes, including sympathetic activation and age, to complement the current study's findings on stress and age as risk factors. However, this review is not statistical. The current study adds a complete, real-world assessment of surgical procedures' POI incidence and risk variables after examining the literature.

Clinical Implications: POI's great incidence in our study shows its importance in patient treatment and recovery. POI slows bowel function and requires intravenous fluid support and nasogastric tube placement, which lengthens hospital stays and complicates recovery. This prolonged recovery raises healthcare costs and harms patients' physical and emotional health. Understanding POI's causes may help doctors predict and treat it, improving patient outcomes and healthcare resource efficiency.

Recommendations for Clinical Practice: Multiple clinical suggestions can be made using the results. Preventative interventions should be prioritised for elderly or colorectal surgery patients. These treatments could include early mobilisation, multimodal analgesia, and early enteral feeding, which have been shown to reduce POI. Diabetes and high blood pressure must be managed to lower the chance of POI. The ERAS (Enhanced Recovery after Surgery) guidelines are meant to help people heal faster from surgery and lower their risk of getting an infection after a number of surgeries.

Strengths of the Study Design and Methodology: There are many good things about the way the study was set up that make it reliable and useful. The reliability and validity of the sample were improved by rules that only allowed patients who met

certain standards to take part. This study looked at people aged 18 and up who had elective abdominal treatments at a single hospital to find out how common postoperative ileus (POI) was and what factors were linked to it. One more strength of a good electronic medical records system is that it gathers a lot of information. It was very important to get detailed information about patients' demographics, operation types, and other health problems before, during, and after surgery in order to evaluate POI. You can use descriptive and inferential statistics to look into how variables are related and to find key risk factors. The results of this study can be used in many surgical settings because they look at POI frequency and risk factors in great detail.

Limitations, Including Potential Biases and Generalizability: The study is worth considering, although there are some drawbacks. The retrospective design may bring biases including missing or erroneous medical data. Retrospective studies risk bias owing to documentation errors because they use previously gathered data. Due to the study's single-center approach, the results cannot be generalised. Research from one hospital or location may not be representative of others, limiting generalizability. The study excluded emergency procedures and discharges against medical advice, thus selection bias may have occurred. These exclusions may underestimate or exaggerate POI frequency and risk variables because emergency cases and early discharges may have different POI profiles than elective treatments.

We should interpret the study's conclusions with caution due to these limitations. Future research should repeat the study at multiple institutions and include more patients to improve generalizability.

Future Research: Future research should use prospective studies to confirm these findings and identify other POI factors. To understand POI in diverse healthcare contexts, the study should include more centres. This would improve results generalizability. Studying the efficacy of ERAS protocol components and how they are used in clinical settings could enhance postoperative care.

Longitudinal studies that track patients over time to establish long-term outcomes like readmission rates

and recovery trajectories after POI could assist understand the greater effects of POI on patient health and healthcare resource use.

Conclusion

This study examines POI rates in elective abdominal surgery patients. Age and comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension are key risk factors for POI. POI occurs in 23% of surgeries; however it is much higher in colorectal procedures. By using a well-defined sample and comprehensive data collection methods, the study identified important risk factors for POI and highlighted the impact of surgical type and patient characteristics on postoperative outcomes. Retrospective design and single-center method are study drawbacks, but extensive examination of operations and risk variables makes up for them.

Reference

1. Venara, P. Alfonsi, E. Cotte, J. Loriau, J. F. Hamel, and K. Slim, "Postoperative ileus concealing intra-abdominal complications in enhanced recovery programs—a retrospective analysis of the GRACE database," *International Journal of Colorectal Disease*, vol. 34, pp. 71-83, 2019.
2. R. Matsui, K. Nagakari, M. Igarashi, R. Hatta, T. Otsuka, J. Nomoto, ... & Y. Ishizaki, "Impact of post-operative paralytic ileus on postoperative outcomes after surgery for colorectal cancer: a single-institution, retrospective study," *Surgery Today*, vol. 52, no. 12, pp. 1731-1740, 2022.
3. Venara, H. Meillat, E. Cotte, M. Ouaisi, E. Duchalais, C. Mor-Martinez, ... & S. Dileon, "Incidence and risk factors for severity of postoperative ileus after colorectal surgery: a prospective registry data analysis," *World Journal of Surgery*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 957-966, 2020.
4. T. Fujimoto, T. Manabe, K. Yukimoto, Y. Tsuru, H. Kitagawa, K. Okuyama, ... & H. Noshiro, "Risk factors for postoperative paralytic ileus in advanced-age patients after laparoscopic colorectal surgery: a retrospective study of 124 consecutive patients," *Journal of the Anus, Rectum and Colon*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 30-37, 2023.
5. R. Harnsberger, J. A. Maykel, and K. Alavi, "Postoperative ileus," *Clinics in Colon and Rectal Surgery*, vol. 32, no. 03, pp. 166-170, 2019.
6. D. Greco, C. C. Petro, J. D. Thomas, K. Montelione, C. Tu, A. Fafaj, ... & A. Prabhu, "Ileus rate after abdominal wall reconstruction: a retrospective analysis of two clinical trials," *Hernia*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 1591-1598, 2022.
7. L. Traeger, M. Koullouros, S. Bedrikovetski, H. M. Kroon, J. W. Moore, and T. Sammour, "Global cost of postoperative ileus following abdominal surgery: meta-analysis," *BJS Open*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. zrad054, 2023.
8. Z. L. Li, B. C. Zhao, W. T. Deng, P. P. Zhuang, W. F. Liu, C. Li, and K. X. Liu, "Incidence and risk factors of postoperative ileus after hysterectomy for benign indications," *International Journal of Colorectal Disease*, vol. 35, pp. 2105-2112, 2020.
9. Y. Namba, Y. Hirata, S. Mukai, S. Okimoto, S. Fujisaki, M. Takahashi, ... & H. Ohdan, "Clinical indicators for the incidence of postoperative ileus after elective surgery for colorectal cancer," *BMC Surgery*, vol. 21, p. 1-6, 2021.
10. L. Greenberg, Y. M. Kelly, R. E. McKay, M. G. Varma, and A. Sarin, "Risk factors and outcomes associated with postoperative ileus following ileostomy formation: a retrospective study," *Perioperative Medicine*, vol. 10, pp. 1-8, 2021.
11. N. R. Hendrickson, Y. Zhang, L. Amofo, Z. Randell, M. Rasmussen, M. Zeidan, ... & W. R. Spiker, "Risk factors for postoperative ileus in patients undergoing spine surgery," *Global Spine Journal*, p. 21925682221075056, 2023.
12. C. Quiroga-Centeno, K. A. Jerez-Torra, P. A. Martin-Mojica, S. A. Castaneda-Alfonso, M. E. Castillo-Sanchez, O. F. Calvo-Corredor, and S. A. Gómez-Ochoa, "Risk factors for prolonged postoperative ileus in colorectal surgery: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *World Journal of Surgery*, vol. 44, pp. 1612-1626, 2020.
13. H. Nguyen, O. J. Bono, and J. V. Bono, "Decreasing incidence of postoperative ileus following total knee arthroplasty: a 17-year retrospective review of 38,007 knee replacements at one institution," *The Journal of Knee Surgery*, vol. 33, no. 08, pp. 750-753, 2020.
14. M. Forbes, A. C. Chehroudi, M. Mannas, A. Bisailon, T. Hong, A. I. So, ... & P. C. Black, "Defining postoperative ileus and associated risk factors in patients undergoing radical cystectomy with an Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) program," *Canadian Urological Association Journal*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 33, 2021.
15. S. Solanki, R. C. Chakinala, K. F. Haq, J. Singh, M. A. Khan, D. Solanki, ... & W. S. Aronow, "Paralytic ileus in the United States: a cross-sectional study from the national inpatient sample," *SAGE Open Medicine*, vol. 8, p. 2050312120962636, 2020.